

ESCAPE Collaboration Distributed Computing Roadmap

Position Statement for the Medium-Term Plan 2026–2030

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Executive summary

This technical position note describes the medium-term plan of the ESCAPE Collaboration for the period 2026–2030, with particular reference to the activities of the Data Infrastructure for Open Science (DIOS) and Virtual Research Environments (VRE) working groups. It builds on the [ESCAPE Collaboration Distributed Computing Roadmap of March 2024](#) and consolidates the technical and operational priorities expressed, through a structured cross-RI gap analysis, by the ESCAPE Research Infrastructures (ERIs) active in the working groups.

The note identifies six priority pillars: Data Lakes and Workflow Management; Metadata Management; Astronomy Interoperability; Virtual Research Environments and Heterogeneous Computing; Authentication, Authorisation and Identity Management; and Artificial Intelligence for Scientific Applications. Financial, human, and environmental sustainability is treated as a cross-cutting concern across all six pillars.

The roadmap further ranks twenty-one concrete activities by their level of cross-community endorsement, and articulates a strategic vision in which ESCAPE consolidates a shared technology stack while preserving each ERI's pace, autonomy, and scientific objectives.

The plan is organised around three objectives: Operation, Consolidation, and Evolution; it is grounded in the principle that a federated computing model should enable researchers to leverage heterogeneous resources without significant overhead, in alignment with the broader European federated-computing landscape (such as the WLCG, the EuroHPC Federation Platform initiative, and the EOSC Federation).

Introduction

Since the conclusion of the Horizon 2020 project phase (2019–2023), ESCAPE has continued its activities as an Open Collaboration of research infrastructures sharing distributed-computing technologies, data-management tools, and analysis platforms. ERIs across astronomy, astroparticle, nuclear and particle physics increasingly share the same operational challenges, such as exabyte-scale data, distributed sites, heterogeneous resources, and converge on a common technology stack, for instance: Rucio for data management, FTS for asynchronous third-party transfers, DIRAC and PaNDA for workflow management, REANA for reproducibility pipelines, and INDIGO IAM for identity management.

The wider European federated-computing landscape reinforces this direction. The WLCG continues to shape distributed computing in high-energy physics and beyond; the EuroHPC Federation Platform is consolidating high-performance computing resources under a federated model; and the EOSC Federation aims to democratise computing capabilities across the broader Open Science ecosystem. The ESCAPE programme is positioned at the intersection of these three federations and intends to align its activities accordingly.

*“**Strengthened collaboration** across particle physics, nuclear physics, astrophysics and cosmology, supported by shared technology development and theoretical interpretation, will be key to unlocking the full potential of these endeavours. **Europe should continue to provide strong support for these activities.**”*

— [CERN-ESU-2025-002](#)

The present plan builds on the foundations established during the ESCAPE project phase: an Exabyte-scale data-management prototype, the blueprint of a Virtual Research Environment integrating shared services, and the adoption of common tools — most notably Rucio — well beyond their originating community. It is guided by the recognition that scientific computing increasingly rewards economies of scale, technical, financial and organisational. Furthermore, the co-development of shared infrastructure and tools limits the duplication of solutions and of support systems required to achieve common objectives, and reduces the operational and technical overhead from individual ERIs.

Strategic technical pillars for the period 2026–2030

The gap analysis conducted with the contributing ERIs has consolidated the cross-community technical and operational needs of the period into six priority pillars. The first five are ranked in the following section by their level of community endorsement; the sixth, Artificial Intelligence for scientific applications, is an emerging area, addressed under Future Directions. These items are summarised in Table 1.

The analysis, and subsequent planning of activities are organised around three objectives: Operation, Consolidation, and Evolution. These objectives are described below, together with the related operational risks.

1. Operation: uniting sites and ERIs around a shared infrastructure and operating it as a single community.

Risk: loss of awareness, within individual ERIs or sites, of the existence and value of the shared infrastructure.

2. Consolidation: hardening the common stack so that it can be deployed by each ERI without significant operational overhead.

Risk: an assumption that a single configuration can serve every community without adaptation.

3. Evolution: developing new capabilities that benefit multiple communities and that avoid duplication of effort across the federation.

Risk: the development of capabilities that are nominally available to all ERIs but adopted by few.

The overarching topic of financial, human, and environmental **sustainability** cuts across all six pillars.

On the human and organisational side, the shared infrastructure model reduces duplication of development and operational effort; tools maintained by a broad, cross-community contributor base enable a longer effective lifetime and lower per-RI overhead.

On the environmental side, energy-aware scheduling, power accounting, network optimisation, and the reduction of embodied carbon are active areas of work across the ERIs, with dedicated initiatives such as the [WLCG Environmental Sustainability Forum](#) and the [SEAMS](#) project already contributing to this effort.

Priority pillar	Scope	Endorsement
Data Lakes and Workflow Management	Hardening of federated Rucio deployments, with a reduction of project-specific patches; native interoperability between data-management and workload-management systems (DIRAC, PanDA, HTCondor, REANA); and a shared operational model across ERIs.	Unanimous
Metadata Management	Integration of Rucio-internal catalogues with external science-metadata databases; domain-specific extensions (gravitational waves, multi-messenger astronomy, neutrino astrophysics, HSF Conditions Database); and common discovery APIs from metadata query to data download.	Unanimous
Astronomy Interoperability (IVOA)	Adoption of Virtual Observatory protocols and integration with IVOA registries; exposure of Rucio-managed data and VRE services through VO-compliant discovery and access mechanisms.	Astronomy-led
Virtual Research Environments and Heterogeneous Computing	Scaling of VREs from interactive use to distributed compute across local clusters, HPC and cloud; seamless DataLake-to-VRE staging; support for declarative workflows alongside Jupyter notebooks; reproducibility; and unified deployment patterns.	Unanimous
Authentication, Authorisation, Identity Management	Cross-RI AAI stack natively supporting both token-capability and role-based paradigms; abstracted permissions layer; and an enabler for interoperability with the EOSC Federation, EuroHPC, and transatlantic infrastructures.	Unanimous
Artificial Intelligence for Scientific Applications	Lowering the barrier to running AI applications on the shared, federated infrastructure: bridging AI workloads (model training, inference and the broader ML lifecycle) with the data-management, workflow and analysis services that underpin them. Not yet consolidated across ERIs; addressed under Future Directions.	Emerging

Table 1: Breakdown of priorities for the ESCAPE Research Infrastructures.

Priority Ranking for the Period 2026–2030

The twenty-one activities identified in the gap analysis are organised below into three tiers, according to their level of cross-community endorsement, and are presented in Table 2. The “Strategic Backbone” groups those activities without which the rest of the programme would lose coherence. The “Important” tier consists of activities with broad to substantial endorsement, to be addressed behind the Strategic Backbone. The “Exploratory” tier includes targeted activities that are either at an early stage of development or narrow in scope, but for which dedicated effort is expected.

Task identifiers (DIOSx.y, VREx.y) are preserved throughout the document for traceability with the underlying gap analysis. A concise description of every task is given in Appendix A.

Tier	Task ID	Task	Endorsement	Rationale
Strategic Backbone	DIOS1.1	Rucio federating capabilities	Very broad	Reducing project-specific patches is a prerequisite for further work in data management. Direct alignment with the high-impact services agenda of the EOSC Federation.
Strategic Backbone	DIOS2.2	Domain-specific metadata extensions	Unanimous	Underpins science-archive integration, IVOA interoperability, and AI/ML workflows.
Strategic Backbone	VRE3.3	AAI framework (token and role paradigms)	Unanimous	A precondition for VRE interoperability, integration, and policy-driven data access. Warrants its own strategic line.
Strategic Backbone	VRE2.1	VRE scaling to distributed compute	Very broad	Principal user-facing capability of the federated stack. Provides unified access to local clusters, HPC, and cloud resources from within the VRE.
Important	DIOS3.2	Edge and HPC data staging	Very Broad	Mechanisms for staging at edge and HPC sites (volume mounts, copy-based, caching); essential as HPC becomes a dominant compute model.
Important	DIOS1.6	WMS adoption and federation	Broad	Promotes shared adoption of PanDA, DIRAC, and REANA; supports economies of scale and aligns DIOS-1 with VRE-2.

Important	DIOS2.1	Rucio-internal and external metadata DB integration	Broad	Complementary to DIOS2.2; together they constitute the metadata envelope of the programme.
Important	DIOS1.2	Rucio – DIRAC integration	Broad	Pragmatic, bounded cross-RI item; removes per-RI glue code.
Important	VRE3.1	Declarative workflows alongside Jupyter	Broad	Support for engines such as Snakemake to complement Jupyter and to enable reproducible, scalable analyses.
Important	VRE3.2	Unified deployment charts and community environments	Broad	Convergence on the modular umbrella Helm Chart; balances Docker-layer efficiency with CVMFS-based software distribution.
Important	VRE3.4	Reproducibility and CVMFS software distribution	Broad	Preserved and reproducible analysis workflows; consolidation of software-distribution patterns across the federation.
Important	VRE1.2	VO tools, Rucio, and VRE integration	Broad	Astronomy-led activity with cross-RI uptake; exposes Rucio-managed data and VRE services through VO-compliant access mechanisms.
Important	VRE2.3	Seamless DataLake-to-VRE data staging	Substantial	Bridge between DIOS-1 and VRE-2. A dedicated workshop with the Rucio team is foreseen as a near-term action.
Important	DIOS3.3	Content delivery and latency hiding	Substantial	Latency-sensitive workflows (notably CTAO); complements edge and HPC staging activities.
Important	VRE2.2	WMS integration in VRE	Substantial	Notebook-driven batch submission through DIRAC or HTCondor; situated at the DIOS-1 / VRE-2 boundary.

Important	VRE1.1	VO protocol adoption and registries	Substantial	Foundational IVOA primitives for cross-cluster data discovery.
Important	DIOS3.1	FTS protocol evolution	Substantial	Support for modern storage and network backends at federation scale.
Important	DIOS1.4	POSIX-like Rucio namespaces	Substantial	Improved usability for end-users; investigation of non-deterministic LFN-to-PFN mapping.
Exploratory	DIOS1.5	Rucio – Kafka / streaming-aware DM	Targeted	Experimental. Stream-aware data management; complementary to triggerless acquisition (FAIR/CBM) and low-latency gravitational-wave transfers.
Exploratory	DIOS1.3	Rucio – HTCondor integration	Targeted	Data-aware HTCondor scheduling; relevant to transatlantic integration and potentially absorbed into DIOS1.6.
Exploratory	DIOS2.3	Discovery APIs (metadata to download)	Targeted	Niche but high value; suitable for a focused effort with CTAO and SKAO as drivers.
Exploratory	VRE3.5	ML lifecycle tooling and AI integration	Targeted	Anticipated to become fundamental within the planning horizon; currently uneven across ERIs (gravitational-wave and neutrino communities leading).

Table 2: Ranked Priority list for ESCAPE Reserach Infrastructures.

Besides the clearly stated priorities and endorsements from the ERIs, a few outstanding items are reported below.

Metadata management is where demand most exceeds the current offer: DIOS2.2 and DIOS2.1 have broad backing, making metadata a critical area of work for the period.

AAI (VRE3.3) is now treated as a standalone priority: beyond broad community need, maintaining an active dialogue is essential to prevent token profiles (such as WLCG and AARC) from drifting apart, thereby hardening interoperability between facilities and identity providers.

The DataLake-to-VRE interface (VRE2.3) maps to where data management meets the user, and it is crucial to support a user-facing infrastructure through it.

Stream-aware data management (DIOS1.5) and ML lifecycle tooling (VRE3.5) are likely to become central within the period, and are worth starting on now.

Finally, edge and HPC data staging (DIOS3.2) is a strategic priority for many ERIs: as more of the compute moves onto HPC machines, efficient staging of data to edge and HPC nodes is what makes those resources usable.

Strategic Priorities by Research Infrastructure

The above plan is grounded in priorities collected from the ERIs that contributed to the gap analysis: CERN, CTAO, GSI/FAIR, VIRGO/ET, KM3NeT, and SKAO. The summaries below preserve the substance of each contribution and are intended as the authoritative statement of each contributing ERI's direction for the period, and as a basis for cross-community alignment. They are not exhaustive of the wider ESCAPE Collaboration, which extends well beyond these contributors.

The inclusion of new contributions from ERIs, and a dynamic evolution of these recommendations is expected, and encouraged.

CERN

- **Distributed computing evolution.** Maximise the uptake of CERN's foundational technologies in strategic alignment with the needs of the HL-LHC and its experiments: Rucio for data management, REANA for reproducible workflows, and CVMFS for software distribution, so that they robustly support broader scientific use cases across the Federation. Investigate the adoption of large-scale distributed workflow-management systems (PanDA, DIRAC) along the same path. Examine the relationship between the EOSC Federation, WLCG, and the evolving HPC landscape, and the potential for a federated computing model that enables researchers to leverage heterogeneous resources without significant overhead.
- **Next-generation analysis facilities.** Build on the developments of the ESCAPE Virtual Research Environment to deploy a unified VRE ecosystem that integrates interactive and batch compute backends, web-based analysis facilities, and machine-learning platforms. Consolidate access to data products and software environments irrespective of compute backend (on-premises, WLCG, EOSC Federation Nodes, HPC, cloud). Provide a common AAI stack that natively supports different community paradigms (token capabilities and roles) without re-implementation.
- **Open Science and collaborative tools.** Ensure that analysis workflows are reproducible and preserved. Continue to lead the evolution of Enterprise File Sync and Share platforms and of federated protocols such as Open Cloud Mesh, in order to promote frictionless user data exchange and collaborative workflows across the Federation. Strengthen the role of institutional repositories such as Zenodo as central pillars of the Open Science infrastructure, with seamless integration into analysis pipelines.

CTAO

- **Bulk data management.** Rucio operates at the core of the bulk data-management system, ensuring the transfer and preservation of petabyte-scale raw data. Foreseen activities include the prioritisation of transfers of data categories and dynamically selected datasets, and the minimisation of end-to-end latency from ingestion to availability.
- **Data processing.** DIRAC operates as the workload-management system for large-scale processing. Foreseen activities include the improvement of the native integration between Rucio and DIRAC.
- **Metadata and data discovery.** Use of Rucio for the management of science-ready data within the Science Archive, in connection with the Science Archive metadata database. Foreseen activities include the integration of Rucio-internal and Rucio-external metadata databases; the development of options for data discovery and download on top of a Rucio data lake; and the design of common APIs for users and applications, spanning discovery and download.
- **Embargoed data.** Integration of Rucio and external metadata databases with IAM and with Open Policy Agents, in order to implement mixed proprietary and public data-access policies, with interoperability of policy agents across platforms.
- **Data access and analysis.** Interactive analysis in Jupyter notebooks and batch processing from within the VRE; integration of DIRAC and of complementary platforms (for example CANFAR); reusability of analysis workflows.
- **Virtual Observatory interoperability.** Ensure that CTAO public and open datasets are discoverable and ready for download through VO tools and services. Foreseen activities include the integration of Rucio, the VRE, and external metadata databases with the VO.

EST

- **Real-time data processing.** Development of workflows for real-time data processing to reduce the data storage volume and subsequent data reduction time. Studying and adapting best practices from other ERIs.
- **Virtual Observatory interoperability.** Development of procedures for dissemination of EST public and open datasets ready for download through VO tools and services.
- **Virtual Research Environments.** Development of Jupiter notebooks for EST interactive data analysis, including those based on AI approaches. Testing and integration of the tools within the VRE, and making them available to other ERIs with similar tasks.

GSI/FAIR

- **Real-time data processing and streaming.** Development and validation of computing models for continuous, triggerless data acquisition as required by experiments such as CBM. Investigation of the integration of streaming technologies (for example message brokers) with distributed data-management systems, with possible extensions toward stream-aware data management.
- **Computing integration and resource orchestration.** Integration of experiment workflows with heterogeneous resources, including HPC (Slurm-based systems), HTC, and cloud infrastructures. Development of models for dynamic resource provisioning and scheduling,

with tight coupling between experiment control systems and distributed computing environments.

- **Distributed data management and access.** Development of scalable data-management solutions for high-throughput data, including efficient placement, caching, and movement. Evaluation and extension of common tools such as Rucio for FAIR-specific requirements, including high-rate ingestion and streaming use cases.
- **Workflow orchestration and automation.** Design and implementation of end-to-end workflows spanning data acquisition, processing, and analysis. Adoption of, and contribution to, common workflow-management solutions (for example REANA) to support reproducibility and scalability.
- **Virtual Research Environments.** Integration of FAIR experiment tools into the ESCAPE VREs, with support for interactive and large-scale analysis. Investigation of sustainable software-distribution approaches (CVMFS, containers).
- **Interoperability, AAI, and integration with ESCAPE and EOSC services.** Adoption of common APIs, data formats, and authentication/authorisation infrastructures to ensure interoperability with ESCAPE and EOSC services.
- **Sustainability and data lifecycle.** Support for long-term preservation, reproducibility, and efficient resource usage in continuous data-taking environments.

VIRGO / Einstein Telescope

- **Distributed data management.** Expansion of the use of Rucio beyond the current point-to-point h(t) transfers from EGO/Cascina to the Pelican Origin in Louvain, to cover all high-latency transfers (RAW and derived). Definition of the workflow at the experiment-to-Open-Science interface. Exploration of Rucio integration with Kafka for low-latency transfers, with a stretch objective of Rucio as a front-end to Kafka, defining streaming-RSEs. Improvement of Rucio usability for the collaboration through a POSIX-like view of the catalogue. Extension of metadata support for the gravitational-wave community (GPS time, data quality, IVOA). Investigation of Rucio integration with HTCondor for data-aware scheduling, and integration of Rucio as the data-management system for HSF Conditions Database payloads.
- **Virtual Research Environments.** Broadening of VRE-HUB to support a wider array of ESCAPE user communities, with attention to the trade-off between Docker-layer efficiency and a CVMFS-based distribution model. Better integration of full machine-learning lifecycle tools (for example MLflow). Extension of the VRE to integrate CI development workflows. Seamless DataLake-to-VRE staging from the user's perspective, with a dedicated workshop between the Rucio team and the DIOS and VRE working groups foreseen as a near-term action. Integration of the data-management system with Zenodo for publications.
- **AAI and Identity Management.** Extension of the AAI/IAM functionality as required to support Virgo and the Einstein Telescope, and to enable better integration with US infrastructures.

KM3NeT

- **Data Lakes and Workflow Management.** Full implementation of a distributed data-management system based on Rucio and DIRAC, with the development and stabilisation of reproducible workflows.

- **Metadata management and IVOA integration.** Extension and adoption of Virtual Observatory and Very High Energy Open Data Format standards for high-energy neutrino astrophysics; extension of IVOA server use for neutrino data.
- **Artificial intelligence applications.** Implementation of AI-based tools for data generation and analysis.
- **Cross-RI development.** Contribution to inter-RI platforms such as MMODA, ACME, and REANA, with the objective of harmonising the data lifecycle.
- **Authentication, authorisation, and identity management.** Transition to a token-based AAI (specifically IndigoIAM) to manage diverse user levels (internal, expert, non-expert) and to ensure secure, interoperable access across major European computing sites.

SKAO

- **Data Lakes and Workflow Management.** Address the challenges posed by SKAO-scale datasets, including the ingestion and dissemination of individual files at multi-terabyte scale and beyond. Increase the deployability of globally federated Rucio data lakes — including in integration, staging, and production modes — and reduce the reliance on project-specific patches. Collaborate on data-archive structure and on data-lifecycle management. Abstract the interfaces to DMS and workload-management systems in order to match the modular architecture of SRCNet.
- **Metadata management.** Provision of metadata-management tools, IVOA-compliant, for multi-messenger astronomy, loosely coupled to the data-management backbone. Mechanisms for the simultaneous ingestion of data and metadata. Standardised IVOA clients for astronomical data discovery.
- **Virtual Research Environments and heterogeneous computing.** Data staging from Rucio storage into user analysis environments, with assessment of different approaches (copy-based, volume-mount). Provision of generalised container-based science-enabling tools, applications, and software distribution. Archival inclusion of user-derived data products, with appropriate provenance information.
- **Authentication, authorisation, and identity management within EOSC.** OIDC token operations (token request through authorisation code, client credentials, and device code; exchange; introspection) abstracted by an external Auth API service. Abstracted permissions-checking layer configurable for a variety of client services.

Future Directions

Artificial Intelligence for scientific applications

A direction not yet consolidated among the ERIs, but which the working groups propose to take up over the period, concerns the relationship between artificial intelligence and the shared computing infrastructure.

The ambition is not to develop AI methods or models as such, nor to duplicate the role of dedicated initiatives such as [RAISE](#), but rather to **lower the barrier to the application of AI on the shared, federated infrastructure**.

The objective is to bridge the gap between the AI applications that the scientific communities are increasingly adopting and the data-management, workflow, and analysis services that underpin them, so that model training, inference, and the broader machine-learning lifecycle can be executed on the federated stack with the same low overhead targeted for conventional workflows.

This evolution would mirror the trajectory of Rucio within ESCAPE. Rucio was consolidated as a shared, beyond-HEP data-management service through sustained cross-community investment, to the benefit of communities that did not need to develop a bespoke solution of their own.

ESCAPE aims to foster a common, infrastructure-level capability building on the machine-learning lifecycle tooling and AI-integration activities already identified (VRE3.5) and on the heterogeneous-computing work of the Virtual Research Environments pillar.

Cross-Cluster Synergies

The present plan does not exist in isolation. Two specific opportunities for cross-cluster synergy are noted for the period.

Interaction with the PaNOSC Science Cluster: iCAT and Rucio integration. In the context of the [InCAEM project](#), which counts PIC and the ALBA synchrotron among its partners, correlative analysis between beamlines and electron-microscopy installations introduces a natural integration point between [iCAT](#), the primary metadata catalogue for photon and neutron RIs, and Rucio. Specific integration avenues include the triggering of transfers upon raw-data registration, the publication of data while preserving access rights, the use of iCAT as a metadata catalogue for Rucio, and the construction of an iCAT federation capable of managing data between sites in line with Photon-Sciences standard metadata.

Citizen Science. The Open Data assets and the VRE platforms of ESCAPE are well-positioned to support citizen-science engagements that bring scientific data to broader audiences, with low-friction reuse paths through Zenodo and through VO-compliant tooling.

Outlook

The objective of the ESCAPE programme for the period 2026–2030 is the consolidation of a shared, federated computing landscape that delivers more than the sum of its parts. Convergence on and consolidation of a shared technology stack — Rucio data lakes, FTS, IAM, REANA, DIRAC, PaNDA, and JupyterHub-based VREs — combined with a ranked allocation of effort, supports an operational model in which each Research Infrastructure pursues its own scientific objectives while contributing to, and benefiting from, common solutions.

The plan is supported by a sustained cadence of coordinated cross-RI data and analysis challenges, by continued investment in joint operations forums, and by a clear alignment of the ESCAPE programme with the wider European federations such as WLCG, EuroHPC, and the EOSC Federation.

This medium-term roadmap is defined by need rather than by funding: the priorities set out above reflect the technical and operational requirements of the ERIs, independently of where support may come from. The collaboration does not aspire to resolve every challenge at once, but to pursue and align funding opportunities as they arise, with an agreed set of priorities ready to act upon.

Above all, the period 2026–2030 is to be defined by collaboration. The ERIs act as collaborators by design and as consumers of a common, shared infrastructure, coordinating their efforts so that development is pooled rather than duplicated.

Appendix A — Task Catalogue

The twenty-one activities ranked in this document are listed in Table 3, grouped by priority area, with a concise description of each. Task identifiers are consistent with those used in the Priority Ranking and with the underlying cross-RI gap analysis.

Task ID	Task	Description
DIOS-1 — Evolution of Data Lakes and Workflow Management		
DIOS1.1	Rucio federating capabilities	Harden the federated Rucio deployment model, reduce project-specific patches, and support integration, staging and production modes across RIs.
DIOS1.2	Rucio – DIRAC integration	Improve native interoperability between Rucio (data management) and DIRAC (workload management) so that data-aware workflows run without per-RI glue code.
DIOS1.3	Rucio – HTCondor integration	Make HTCondor data-aware through Rucio; investigate job submission triggering replication.
DIOS1.4	POSIX-like Rucio namespaces	Provide intuitive, POSIX-like views of the Rucio catalogue for end users; investigate non-deterministic LFN-to-PFN mapping.
DIOS1.5	Rucio – Kafka / streaming-aware DM	Extend Rucio to be aware of stream-broker endpoints; explore streaming RSEs.
DIOS1.6	WMS adoption and federation	Foster federated adoption of PanDA, DIRAC and REANA; establish a shared operational model across RIs and reduce duplication.
DIOS-2 — Metadata Management		
DIOS2.1	Rucio-internal and external metadata DB integration	Integrate Rucio's internal catalogues with external science-metadata databases, such as science archives.
DIOS2.2	Domain-specific metadata extensions	Extend Rucio to store gravitational-wave (GPS time, data quality), multi-messenger, neutrino and HSF Conditions Database metadata, with intuitive client access.
DIOS2.3	Discovery APIs: metadata to download	Common APIs moving users and applications from complex metadata queries to ready-to-download data.
DIOS-3 — Edge Services and HPC Integration		
DIOS3.1	FTS protocol evolution	Evolve transfer protocols to support modern storage and network backends at federation scale.

DIOS3.2	Data staging at edge and HPC nodes	Mechanisms for staging data at edge and HPC sites (volume mounts, copy-based, caches) to support heterogeneous compute.
DIOS3.3	Content delivery and latency hiding	Latency-hiding mechanisms, prioritised transfers and content-delivery optimisations for latency-sensitive workflows.
VRE-1 — Integration with the broader IVOA		
VRE1.1	VO protocol adoption and registries	Adopt VO protocols for interoperability with IVOA registries and VO tools.
VRE1.2	VO tools, Rucio and VRE integration	Expose Rucio-managed data and VRE services through VO-compliant discovery and access mechanisms.
VRE-2 — Virtual Research Environments and Heterogeneous Computing		
VRE2.1	Scaling interactive to distributed compute	Unified access to local clusters, HPC and cloud from within the VRE, beyond the current interactive-only model.
VRE2.2	WMS integration in VRE	Bring DIRAC and HTCondor job submission into Jupyter-based VREs so that users drive batch processing from notebooks.
VRE2.3	Seamless DataLake-to-VRE data staging	Natural, user-transparent data access from the VRE to the Rucio DataLake; clarify mount, client and TPC-via-FTS approaches.
VRE-3 — VRE Evolution		
VRE3.1	Declarative workflows alongside Jupyter	Support Snakemake and other declarative workflow engines inside the VRE for reproducible, scalable analyses.
VRE3.2	Unified deployment charts and community environments	Common deployment artefacts; balance Docker-layer efficiency with CVMFS-based software distribution.
VRE3.3	AAI framework (token and role paradigms)	Cross-RI AAI stack natively supporting token-capability and role-based models; an enabler for transatlantic interoperability and data-access policies.
VRE3.4	Reproducibility and CVMFS software distribution	Preserved, reproducible analysis workflows; consolidate software-distribution patterns across the federation.
VRE3.5	ML lifecycle tools and AI integration	Integration of full ML lifecycle tooling (e.g. MLflow) in the VRE; support for AI-based analysis pipelines.

Table 3: Catalogue of technical focus activities identified by the ESCAPE Research Infrastructures.